

CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION QUALITIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Improving the system of protecting and strengthening children's health, forming a culture of health and motivation for a healthy lifestyle in them should become one of the priority directions of the activities of the preschool educational organization. The article discusses about physical education of preschool children.*

Keywords: *physical education of preschool children, health, healthy child, physical development.*

Education of physical qualities is one of the main aspects of physical education. Physical education of preschool children has a special place in the general system of education and training. An important task that determines the importance of physical education as the basis of all-round development is the formation of a healthy child who knows his movements well, likes physical exercises, and is independently oriented to his environment.

The whole set of physical education tools, including the implementation of daily routines, health and fitness activities, provision of necessary physical loads, rational nutrition should be aimed at the main task - raising a healthy child. It is possible to achieve the main tasks of education and recreation only by implementing a comprehensive approach: Physical education of preschool children should exclude a system of physical exercises that bring positive emotions to the child, stressful situations and fear of performing activities.

Organizational forms of physical education work in preschool educational organizations are as follows:

- physical education; daily physical education and health activities (morning exercises, outdoor and sports games, minutes of physical education, tempering exercises combined with physical exercises);
- active recreation (sports events, sports holidays, health days, hiking trips);
- independent motor activity of children;
- family work.

Independent motor activity of preschool children continues under the supervision of a naturalist. The content and duration of physical exercises are determined by the children themselves. The nature of this activity depends on the individual information, readiness, capabilities and interests of preschool children. A successful solution to the problems of physical education is possible only by implementing an individual approach to children in the interrelated work of the preschool education organization and the family. All forms and types of work are interrelated and complement each other. Together, they create the necessary motor regime that provides the child with daily physical education.

In the process of physical education, teaching children to move is carried out under the direct guidance of the educator and the independent activities of children under his supervision. When teaching movement activities, the child's cognitive, willful and emotional powers are

developed and his practical movement skills are formed. Teaching actions to the child's inner world feeling, thinking, gradually forming worldview, moral qualities; purposefully affects the activities of children, which are useful for health and general physical development. The content of education consists of physical exercises and dynamic games selected based on the state requirements for the education of children of preschool age. In the process of education, adults give children the experience of goal-oriented activities. Its content also includes the experience of mastering actions that serve its development and improvement.

In the process of training movement activities, adults (parents, educators) set new movement tasks for children, taking into account the psychophysiological characteristics of children's development. The child's ability to solve new movement tasks in the course of exercises and the great opportunities that arise in connection with this change the nature and quality of movements. What is very characteristic for this age period acquires a new quality in the process of teaching new exercises. For example, a child's gait is completely different at the beginning and at the end of the second year. This phenomenon can be shown as a didactic denial of the old by the new, an objective condition of all development and conflict resolution, a moving factor.

Improving the system of protecting and strengthening children's health, forming a culture of health and motivation for a healthy lifestyle in them should become one of the priorities of the activities of the preschool educational organization. It is necessary to ensure that the modern educational concept not only improves preschool children, but also provides a personal approach to the educational environment.

The basis of the child's physical health should be considered the level of development and characteristics of his organs and systems. The level of development is determined by a program that is specific to the nature of each child and is related to his basic needs. This is the satisfaction of basic needs, which is a condition for the child's individual development. A prerequisite for the complete mental health of children is a state of mental comfort and psychological well-being that ensures adequate regulation of their behavior in the process of various activities. This situation is determined by the needs of the child and the possibilities of meeting them. The spiritual component of human health is characterized by their attitude to the educational process, as well as their compliance with generally accepted norms of behavior, which are directly related to the development of motivational and semantic areas of a preschool child. Thus, in the process of teaching actions, mental abilities, moral and aesthetic feelings develop in children, a conscious attitude to their activities and, in connection with this, striving for a goal, organization is formed.

The main tasks of physical education of children of preschool age in preschool education organizations and in the family are to make them healthy and strong, to train their body, to organize education and upbringing correctly. Health care tasks of preschool children are the main task of physical education, which consists of protecting the child's life, strengthening his health, protecting himself by exercising his body, and increasing resistance to various diseases. All of this is the implementation of a general approach to the educational process in interrelationship. This process serves to form a comprehensively developed person.

It should be noted that for certain methodological recommendations for a practitioner, basic actions of preschool children established in research, age characteristics related to the formation and development of physical qualities, there are not enough scientific-methodical literature and programs based on it.

Accordingly, in our opinion, one of the main principles of physical education is physical principle of age adequacy. Educational directions are the priority of this process development in accordance with the age of a person in its various stages. The principle that forces to change according to the trends is enough. According to L. E. Lyubomsky and others, an analysis of existing preschool education programs related to the education and upbringing of children indicates that the main task of physical activities, conducted in the form of basic movements, is to facilitate development. To achieve this goal, a wide range of physical exercises and active games, along with comprehensive educational material, is typically presented.

At the same time, there is a noticeable lack of attention to the need for targeting physical qualities in preschool education, particularly in relation to physical education duties within preschool institutions. The training program for children aims to improve agility, quickness, endurance, and strength; however, specific notes about compatibility are often absent. Experts suggest that this oversight can complicate the development of physical skills during preschool years. Testing the quality level of movement in five- to seven-year-old children often yields inconclusive results, as it remains unclear whether these results are related to the children's existing physical capabilities or to their age characteristics, which may influence rates of development. Furthermore, there is insufficient literature available on the complex development of movement qualities for preschool-aged children.

Summary.

A number of authors note that during preschool age, children actively engage in controlling their own bodies, which involves the coherence of movements and activities, as well as the formation of body structure while managing and valuing it. However, several unresolved issues related to children's physical education and mental development exist in this age group. These include, in particular:

- The use of a wide variety of movement games in the physical education system for preschool children, which is not implemented based on careful planning for their physical quality development.

- The problem of developing physical qualities through mobile games, taking into account the age and gender of 3- to 6-year-old children, remains unresolved.

- A comprehensive plan for using action games aimed at developing physical qualities has not been developed.

- Finally, we could not find identified scientific works that analyze the characteristics of the interaction of physical qualities in children aged 3 to 6 years across different ages and sexes based on in-depth coordination analysis.

In our opinion, addressing these problems is crucial for improving the system of children's physical education, both theoretically and practically.

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